

1 Anticipating the impact of pitfalls in kinetic biodegradation parameter estimation from
2 substrate depletion curves of organic pollutants

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9
10 ABSTRACT

11 Accurate and reliable estimation of kinetic parameters of pollutant biodegradation processes is essential for
12 environmental and health risk assessment. Common biodegradation models proposed in the literature, such as
13 the nonlinear Monod equation and its simplified versions (e.g. Michaelis-Menten-like and first-order
14 equations), are problematic in terms of accuracy of kinetic parameters due to the parameter correlation.
15 However, a comparison between these models in terms of accuracy and reliability, related to data imprecision,
16 has not been performed in the literature. This task is necessary, mainly because the model selection cannot be
17 straightforward, as shown in this work. To facilitate the comparison, novel statistics summarising the accuracy
18 and reliability of estimations are introduced. The main objective is to establish relationships between these
19 statistics (through new diagnostic indicators) to limit the probability of pitfalls or to avoid the negative impact
20 of an improper model selection. Such anticipation is an imperative need in the biodegradation modelling
21 framework and, to the best of our knowledge, it has never been performed. In order to account for accuracy,
22 simulated data in realistic conditions are used to highlight the magnitude of pitfalls related to the model
23 selection for estimation of the main kinetic parameters (K_s , μ_m and/or V_m). Four scenarios related to model
24 selection are compared for the first time and, diagnostic indicators able to anticipate relevant aspects related
25 to accuracy and reliability are introduced. Moreover, first evidences of the impact of measurement errors in
26 other intrinsic Monod parameters (the initial biomass concentration and the microbial yield coefficient, Y), as
27 well as the impact of the simultaneous μ_m , K_s and Y estimation, on the accuracy and reliability of the
28 estimations are reported. Despite the pitfalls shown, specific applicability of even unreliable models is
29 highlighted, and suggestions for environmental and health risk modellers are provided accordingly.

30 **Capsule:** The accuracy degree of biodegradation parameter estimation from substrate depletion curves of
31 organic pollutants is anticipated using diagnostic indicators calculated from models.

32
33 **Keywords:**

34 Biodegradation
35 Modelling depletion curve
36 Parameter estimations
37 Pitfalls
38 Model comparison

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43 1. Introduction

44 Organic pollutants, such as pharmaceuticals and personal care products, can reach aquatic
45 environment as a result of anthropogenic activities (e.g. industrial discharges, discharges of treated
46 effluents from domestic and hospital wastewater treatment plants, sewer leaking, etc.) (Tran and Gin,
47 2017; Liao et al., 2018). Some of these compounds can persist in the environment if their
48 physicochemical degradation and/or biodegradation are slow, which depends, among other factors,
49 on their physicochemical properties and chemical structure (Tran et al., 2015). This persistence
50 (related to (bio)degradation half-lives) could cause their accumulation in the environment and biota
51 and chronic effects (Pizzo et al., 2016). Biodegradation processes, which constitute a nature's waste
52 management and a recycling system, have been extensively exploited by man in diverse treatment
53 systems (e.g. in waste water treatment plants, bioremediation) to attenuate the environmental impact
54 and the health risk caused by contaminants (Okpokwasili and Nweke, 2005). Biodegradation, which
55 can take place under two mechanisms, metabolic and co-metabolic degradation, depends on the
56 microbial consortia and also on the presence of primary substrates (Tran et al., 2013). Several
57 microbial growth and biodegradation kinetic models have been proposed in the literature to describe
58 the metabolism dynamics of compounds exposed to pure microorganisms cultures or microbial
59 populations from the natural environment (Okpokwasili and Nweke, 2005).

60 Accurate and reliable estimations of kinetic parameters related to *in vitro* substrate
61 biodegradation experiments are essential not only to understand the phenomena but also to predict
62 and design the performance of field-scale biological treatment systems (Goudar and Ellis, 2001), as
63 well as for hazard determination (persistence) (Kowalczyk et al., 2015). Among the biodegradation
64 models proposed to perform the estimation of kinetic parameters from the substrate concentration (S)
65 data over time (t) (S-t data, substrate depletion curve), the Monod equation and its simplified versions,
66 i.e. the Michaelis-Menten-like equation and the first-order equation, are the most used (Goudar and
67 Ellis, 2001; Liu and Zachara, 2001; Robinson and Tiedje, 1983). Table 1 (more detailed in Table S1;
68 supplementary data) summarises the equations, the corresponding nomenclature, common strategies
69 proposed for parameter estimation, as well as the limitations reported in the literature. The Monod
70 equation has been widely used to describe microbial growth-linked biodegradation of substrate, in
71 which the rates of the microbial growth and substrate degradation are related. Conversely, the
72 simplified versions of Monod are valid in situations where the organism concentration remains
73 essentially constant even as the substrate is degraded (i.e. no-growth biodegradation) (Okpokwasili
74 and Nweke, 2005).

75 Accuracy and reliability of the estimations of kinetic parameters are mainly affected by three
76 factors. Culture history and experimental procedure influence the affinity of the microorganisms

77 towards the substrate and their adaptation. The correlation of parameters provokes lack of uniqueness
78 (i.e. multiple paired solutions fitting the S-t data; thus, lack of parameter identifiability) and instability
79 (i.e. high sensitivity of the estimated parameters to errors of measurement, e.g. S data imprecision)
80 (Liu and Zachara, 2001). Covariance ellipses showing parameter correlation, model prediction
81 uncertainty or residuals analysis have been suggested to diagnose the reliability of the model
82 (Robinson J.A, 1985). However, inaccuracy is not accounted for.

83 Optimal experimental conditions that minimise the mathematical uncertainties of the Monod
84 parameter estimates have been proposed (Liu and Zachara, 2001). However, the application of these
85 conditions would require previous knowledge about the Monod kinetic parameters and the S-
86 imprecision level. When this information is unknown, the most likely situation, multiple
87 biodegradation experiments varying the experimental conditions are proposed to find the combination
88 of conditions that provide estimates expected to be reliable (Helbling et al., 2014; Liu and Zachara,
89 2001). However, a real guaranty of accuracy has not been established. An alternative to this tedious
90 and costly procedure is the use of simulated data obtained from prefixed kinetic parameters (Liu and
91 Zachara, 2001; Robinson and Tiedje, 1983). In fact, simulation is the unique strategy able to establish
92 accuracy, and therefore, to open the possibilities of defining accuracy-statistics relationships. For
93 instance, a comparison between the errors in the estimated parameters and the residual sum of squares
94 of S data has been established by simulation studies (Robinson and Tiedje, 1983).

95 Kinetic model selection or validity is frequently justified just by a reasonably good
96 determination coefficient (R^2), as for instance in Li and Zhang (2010). As an alternative strategy, the
97 standard deviation associated to the estimated parameters has been proposed to state their reliability,
98 based on Michaelis-Menten-like (solved with the Lambert W function) (Goudar and Ellis, 2001) or
99 Monod models (Liu and Zachara, 2001). However, in the literature dealing with kinetic
100 biodegradation models, there is a lack of evidences regarding the correlation between curve fitting or
101 uncertainty statistics and accuracy, when a given kinetic model is selected. In most cases, the
102 verification of the assumptions made by the selected kinetic model (see Table S1) is neglected. In
103 addition, mixed phenomena could make difficult to assure that a concrete model is the best one. For
104 instance, “coincidental” assimilable organic carbon (apart from the target substrate) and
105 “coincidental” microbes may affect the kinetics of biodegradation (Liu et al., 2014). Thus, model
106 selection can become an ambiguous issue. This fact, not previously investigated in the literature,
107 should increase the probability of pitfalls in the parameter estimation process due to incorrect model
108 selection.

109 Accuracy problems in the case of noisy data are unavoidable (i.e. they are intrinsic to the
110 models). Despite this, the preliminary aim of this work is to demonstrate the variety of pitfalls

111 involved in the estimation of the main biodegradation kinetic parameters in the presence of reasonably
112 noisy experimental data. As an illustration, the pitfalls were connected with a correct/incorrect model
113 selection. Moreover, the main aim is to search for anticipative strategies to reduce the impact of such
114 pitfalls. This aim can only be achieved by means of simulation studies. A concrete objective is to
115 evaluate the effect of biodegradation kinetic model selection (correct or incorrect model). For the first
116 time, different scenarios derived from several combinations of equations in Table S1 (for generating
117 simulated error-free data and for estimating the parameters after adding noise to the data) are
118 compared in terms of accuracy and reliability. In this work, reliability takes into account presence of
119 different types of anomalous outputs, uncertainty of the estimated parameters, curve fitting features
120 and degree of dispersion, all related to data imprecision. In order to facilitate the comparison, novel
121 [0-100] fixed-scale indicators summarising the accuracy and reliability of estimations are introduced.
122 Another concrete objective is to establish relationships between the studied statistics enabling to
123 anticipate the probability of pitfalls. In our opinion, such anticipation is an imperative need in the
124 biodegradation modelling framework, and, to the best of our knowledge, it has never been performed.
125 An additional objective is to provide first evidence of the impact of the simultaneous estimation of
126 the main Monod parameters and the microbial yield coefficient, Y , on accuracy and reliability, as
127 well as the impact of measurement systematic errors in the initial biomass concentration and Y .

128

129 **2. Material and methods**

130 *2.1. Simulated S-t data*

131 Tables 1 and S1 include the nomenclature used in this work. For clarity, the estimates of the
132 two main kinetic parameters were called p1 (estimate of the true μ_m or V_m values) and p2 (estimate
133 of the true K_s values). Thus, errors were calculated from the differences between estimates and true
134 values. Simulated substrate concentration (S) data were obtained using conditions similar to those in
135 Robinson and Tiedje (1983) and using dimensionless true parameters as suggested in Liu and Zachara
136 (2001): $\mu_m = V_m = 0.1$, $K_s = 5$. In the current study, $X_0 = Y = 0.2$ were fixed (Eq. (1a) in Table 1 and
137 S1). S_0 (initial substrate concentration) was fixed at different values along the work, so that the $S_0 /$
138 K_s ratios were in the 10^{-3} to 2.5 range. This covered from $S_0 \ll K_s$ values (the so-called first-order
139 region; with a very high impact of the parameter correlation problem (Liu and Zachara, 2001;
140 Robinson and Tiedje, 1983)) to comparable S_0 and K_s values (so-called mixed-order region; with
141 somewhat lower, but still high, impact of the parameter correlation problem (Liu and Zachara, 2001;
142 Robinson and Tiedje, 1983)).

143 For each S_0 value, the following steps were carried out in each simulation:

- 144 1) 25 uniformly spaced S values ranging from S_0 to $0.01 \times S_0$ were established.
- 145 2) t values were calculated from the S values established in step 1, using both Eq. (1a) and (2a)
- 146 ($t = f(S)$). Therefore, two different S-t data sets were generated, simulating growth-linked
- 147 (Eq. (1a)) and no-growth (Eq. (2a)) biodegradation of substrate. Since the calculations are free
- 148 of iterations, the S-t data generated were error-free (Goudar, 2012).
- 149 3) For both S-t data sets, random noise was added to the S data from a value of the relative
- 150 standard deviation in percentage (RSD) prefixed (see further details in section 2.3).
- 151 4) Each S-t data set derived in the step 3 was modelled using both Eq. (1a) (a $t = f(S)$ approach)
- 152 and Eq. (2b) (an $S = f(t)$ approach).
- 153 5) Finally, estimated parameters and related statistics were obtained (a set of 70 variables in total;
- 154 see section 2.3).

155

156 2.2. Scenarios related to ambiguous kinetic model selection

157 Table 1 displays four different scenarios that combine equations related to Monod and

158 Michaelis-Menten-like equations. They represent situations in which biomass growth is not

159 controlled or effectively measured or where an evident biomass growing cannot be linked

160 unequivocally with the target substrate, for instance, due to the presence of “coincidental” carbon

161 source and/or microbes (Liu et al., 2014) or toxicity issues, provoking an ambiguous kinetic model

162 selection (see more details in Table S2 in supplementary data). Each scenario was coded using two

163 numbers in brackets, representing the equations in Table 1 (and S1) used to generate the S-t data

164 (section 2.1; steps 1-3) and to estimate the parameters and their statistics (section 2.1; steps 4 and 5;

165 the model selection stage in a real situation). Thus, the scenarios represent two correct and two

166 incorrect model selection cases for estimating the kinetic parameters.

167

168 2.3. Software and variables

169 For applying the method imprecision to the S data (step 3 of the simulation, section 2.1), a

170 constant standard deviation in repeatability conditions (s_r) was calculated from the fixed RSD and the

171 S-vector mean (i.e. $s_r = \text{RSD} \cdot \text{mean}(S) / 100$). The RANDOM.m function in MATLAB® R2016b

172 (MathWorks, Natick, Massachusetts) was used to calculate a noise vector (with the same length as

173 the S-vector), from the normal distribution, with mean equal to 0 and standard deviation equal to s_r .

174 The noise vector was finally added to the S vector. In the case of negative S values (possible for low

175 S data with high RSD), the corresponding S value was set to 0 (in order to maintain the length of the

176 S-vector constant in all cases).

177 For modelling purposes, the NLINFIT.m function in MATLAB® R2016b (MathWorks,
 178 Natick, Massachusetts) was used. It estimates the coefficients of a nonlinear regression function using
 179 iterative least squares estimation. To solve the explicit Lambert W function (Eq. (2b)), the improved
 180 approximation in Winitzki (2003) was used. Algorithmic details for implementation can be found in
 181 Her et al. (2015).

182 Every individual simulation was characterised by a set of 70 variables. The first ten variables
 183 names (and numbers) correspond to the prefixed conditions: simulation number (1), replicate number
 184 (2), $\mu_m = V_m$ (3), K_s (4), Y (5), X_0 (6), S_0 (7), RSD (8), S_0 / K_s (9) and S_0 / X_0 (10). Then, 14 variables
 185 (estimated parameters and related statistics), per scenario. For scenario [11]: p_1 (11), p_2 (12), p_1 / p_2
 186 (13), determination coefficient, R^2 (14), mean absolute relative error of S , MAE (15), relative
 187 uncertainty for p_1 and p_2 , Up_1 and Up_2 (16 and 17, respectively), Descriptive power, Dp (18), semi-
 188 confidence interval for p_1 and p_2 , ICp_1 and ICp_2 (19 and 20, respectively), relative errors in
 189 percentage of p_1 and p_2 , Ep_1 and Ep_2 (21 and 22, respectively), predictive power of the model, Pp
 190 (23), and predictive power for the S-t curve $Pp(S)$ (24). They are followed by the same 14 variables
 191 for the other scenarios: [22], variables 25 to 38, [12] variables 39 to 52 and [21] variables 53 to 66.
 192 Finally, four variables were obtained from Eq. (3b) (linear regression): R^2 and $Pp(S)$ using the t-S
 193 data generated by Eq. (1a) and (2a), (variables 67 and 68, and 69 and 70, respectively). Table S3 in
 194 supplementary data shows an example of the variable outputs obtained from five simulations per
 195 scenario for the RSD = 0 case.

196 The variable set contains common statistics. Some of them are related to curve fitting
 197 statistics, measuring the goodness-of-fit (i.e. agreement between the simulated and modelled S
 198 values), such as R^2 (based on absolute differences) and MAE (based on relative differences; it is more
 199 sensitive to low S values). Note that as R^2 , MAE is a dimensionless indicator ($MAE = \text{mean}(\text{abs}(E))$;
 200 where $E = 100 * (S_{\text{estimated}} - S) / S$). Other variables are related to the uncertainty of estimates. The semi-
 201 confidence interval is a measure of the absolute uncertainty of a parameter, e.g. $p_1 \pm ICp_1$, and could
 202 be used to express the corresponding relative uncertainty in percentage (e.g. $Up_1 = 100 (ICp_1 / p_1)$).
 203 Also, Ep_1 and Ep_2 are related to accuracy.

204 Other statistics were introduced in this work as [0-100] fixed-scale indicators, to facilitate
 205 their interpretation. Some of them were adapted from multivariate modelling approaches (Sagrado
 206 and Cronin, 2006; Sagrado and Cronin, 2008). The descriptive power of the model (Dp) was
 207 calculated here as:

$$208 \quad Dp = 100 \left(1 - \frac{\frac{Up_1 + Up_2}{100 + 100}}{2} \right) \quad (4)$$

209 Dp is an indicator of the uncertainty of the two estimated parameters (i.e. an indicator of
210 reliability). For IC values equal to zero (no uncertainty; an ideal situation), Dp = 100 (maximum
211 descriptive power). For IC values equal to the parameter estimates (unreliable parameters), Dp = 0
212 (minimum descriptive power). Since there was no interest in discriminating between worse uncertain
213 estimations (i.e. IC values higher than p1 and p2), negative Dp values were set to 0. Thus, the practical
214 interval for Dp is from 0 to 100.

215 The predictive power of the model (Pp) was calculated as:

$$216 \quad Pp = 100 - \left(\frac{|Ep1| + |Ep2|}{2} \right) \quad (5)$$

217 Pp is an indicator of the accuracy of the two estimated parameters. Note that Pp (as the rest of
218 the accuracy variables) requires to know the true values of the kinetic parameters, so it is restricted
219 to simulation studies. For errors equal to zero, Pp = 100 (maximum model accuracy). For errors equal
220 to $\pm 100\%$ (or higher), Pp = 0. Therefore, as before, the practical Pp range is 0 – 100. Combining Pp
221 and Dp in a plot (Pp-Dp plot), the join predictive and descriptive ability of the model can be
222 summarised as a single point. This is interesting for model comparison purposes.

223 Extending the concept of Pp to the predicted S values by a model, the predictive power for the
224 S-t data, Pp(S), was proposed:

$$225 \quad Pp(S) = 100 - MAE \quad (6)$$

226 As before, Pp(S) was set between zero (MAE = 100 or higher) and 100 (MAE = 0; perfect
227 agreement between the experimental-like simulated and modelled S-t data), being then a
228 dimensionless indicator. In this work, Pp(S) was also considered an indicator of the reliability of a
229 model. Additional indicators of reliability as the degree of dispersion of the obtained statistics (due
230 to RSD) and the presence of anomalous outputs were also considered in this work. Table S3 in
231 supplementary data helps to see how the novel statistics (Pp, Dp and Pp(S)) behave compared with
232 those more common. For instance, high outputs (>1000) in scenarios [12] and [21] correspond to zero
233 values for Pp and Dp, which simplifies the data visualization (e.g. a Pp-Dp plot has always a fix 0-
234 100 scale in both axis).

235

236 **3. Results and Discussion**

237 *3.1. Model comparison*

238 In order to perform a model comparison in terms of accuracy and reliability a study comprising
239 500 simulations was carried out (100 simulations per 5 different S_0/K_s values in the 10^{-3} to 2.5 range).

240 Concretely, the $\log(S_0 / K_s)$ values used were: -3, -2, -1, 0, and 0.4, covering from first-order ($S_0 \ll$
241 K_s) to mixed-order ($S_0 \sim K_s$) regions as stated in section 2.1. Other conditions were set as indicated
242 in section 2.1. The variables and novel statistics generated were used to check the validity of the
243 kinetic models. In this section, RSD was fixed to 5 % (as a main source of unreliability). This value
244 was considered a moderate (realistic) overall method imprecision (Escuder-Gilabert et al., 2018).

245

246 3.1.1. Anomalous outputs

247 The amount of anomalous outputs generated during the parameter estimation stage (steps 4
248 and 5 in section 2.1) could be considered as a first indicator of the lack of consistency of the kinetic
249 models depending on the scenario (a first model comparison). The following situations were
250 considered as anomalous: (i) negative p_1 or p_2 estimates (inconsistent model estimates) and (ii)
251 variables with non-available or infinite outputs or with absolute values higher than 10^3
252 (failure/illogical model estimations).

253 As a result of the simulation, it was observed that the presence of anomalous depended on the
254 $\log(S_0 / K_s)$ level. For the right model selection cases, scenarios [11] and [22], the presence of
255 anomalous was mainly restricted to negative $\log(S_0 / K_s)$ values (the first-order region), while in the
256 case of wrong model selection, scenarios [12] and [21], anomalous outputs covered the entire
257 evaluated S_0 / K_s region. Except for the variable MAE, the scenario [22] presented the lowest amount
258 of anomalous. In spite of this, the scenario [22] exhibited the highest frequency of negative p_1 and
259 p_2 values (43 negative outputs); in contrast to the scenario [11] (1 negative output). In the scenario
260 [21], anomalous outputs represented more than the 50 % of the estimations. Anomalous outputs
261 mostly corresponded to the parameter estimates (p_1 , p_2) and their related statistics (U, IC, E and
262 MAE, see section 2.2). The anomalous outputs correspond to repeated simulations in the same
263 conditions. Therefore, they represent pitfalls when using the equations in Table 1 and S1, connected
264 with the lack of reliability associated with RSD. More details of this study can be found in Fig. S1
265 (supplementary data). The non-anomalous parameters estimated during the simulation are shown in
266 the supplementary data (Fig. S2 to S4).

267

268 3.1.2. Pp-Dp plots and Pp(S)-R² plots

269 A Pp-Dp plot is proposed in this work as an efficient way to analyse jointly the accuracy and
270 uncertainty information and to compare the different scenarios. Fig. 1 shows the Pp-Dp plots obtained
271 for each scenario. According to their definitions in section 2.3, values of Pp and Dp close to 100
272 indicate maximum predictive and descriptive power, respectively. An additional advantage of this

273 plot is that extreme outputs removal or axis adjustment is unnecessary since the corresponding Pp
274 and/or Dp values become close to zero when calculated. As can be seen, the scenario [22] shows the
275 best accuracy (high Pp) and uncertainty (high Dp) scores for $\log(S_0 / K_s) = 0.4$. Also, these outputs
276 appear to be more compact (less affected by RSD; more reliable) than for the scenario [11]. On the
277 other hand, for the scenario [11], a numerous group of outputs of $\log(S_0 / K_s) = 0.4$ are concentrated
278 at Pp values of 40 with similar Dp values. This fact deserves more attention (see later in section 3.3).

279 For correct model selection (scenarios [11] and [22]), in general, the lower the $\log(S_0 / K_s)$
280 the higher the dispersion of outputs (lower Pp-Dp correlation). Interestingly, there are results with
281 high Pp and low Dp and vice versa, which indicates that the correlation usually presumed in the
282 literature between accuracy and a narrow confidence interval for the estimates is risky (another pitfall
283 and a new example of lack of reliability). The incorrect model selection (scenarios [12] and [21])
284 leads to poor descriptive and predictive model results.

285 In order to complete the previous information, a novel plot (Pp(S)-R²) was introduced to
286 compare the curve fitting ability of the models (Fig. 2). Pp(S), related to MAE, and the classical R²
287 are not equal statistics, according to their calculation. As can be seen, outputs obtained using Eq. (1a)
288 (scenarios [11] and [21]) are located in the same space in this plot regardless of the $\log(S_0 / K_s)$ value,
289 which indicates a partial Pp(S)-R² correlation. However, in the scenario [21] (incorrect model
290 selection case), the worst results (the lowest R² and Pp(S) outputs) correspond to the highest $\log(S_0$
291 / $K_s)$ level, while scenario [11] (correct model selection case) exhibits the opposite behaviour.
292 Regarding the scenario [22] (correct model selection case), it is noticeable that high R² outputs are
293 obtained in all the simulations, even with Pp(S) data equal to 0. Therefore, the Pp(S)-R² correlation
294 does not exist in this case. This lack of correlation is also evident for the scenario [12] (incorrect
295 model selection case), in which the worst results are obtained for the highest $\log(S_0 / K_s)$ level. On
296 the other hand, the outputs dispersion due to RSD, particularly for Pp(S), is observable (lack of
297 reliability). Comparing the results of Fig. 2 (R² outputs higher than 0.75) and Fig. 1 (Pp outputs from
298 0 to 100), it can be stated that the use of R² to draw conclusions on accuracy (a frequent pitfall
299 observed in the literature) becomes a bad practice, extremely optimistic.

300 The combined use of Pp-Dp and Pp(S)-R² plots has a high diagnostic capacity for model
301 comparison. They can be used to compare model accuracy and reliability under other initial
302 conditions. For instance, Table S4 in supplementary data shows that the use of higher S_0 / K_s ratios
303 does not improve the quality of the results. Table 1 summarises the main results extracted from the
304 kinetic model comparison and the main consequences of correct or incorrect model selection, as well
305 as possible solutions based on anticipative strategies.

306

307 3.2. Anticipative strategies. Diagnostic statistics

308 The results above reveal the influence of the model (scenario) selection, S_0 / K_s ratio (first- or
309 mixed-order region) and overall method imprecision (RSD) on the parameter estimation quality.
310 Since in most real experiments such information is frequently unknown, it would be worth trying to
311 anticipate it to limit its impact. To the best of our knowledge, such study has not been attempted
312 before. The anticipative strategy consisted in defining discriminant functions of the form: $I = \sum (f_i$
313 $V_i)$, where I is the response variable to be discriminated (i.e. an indicator of the unknown
314 information), V_i is a predictive variable showing some discriminant ability for I , and f_i is its weighting
315 factor. The final decision will depend on defining a threshold value for I . To select the best predictive
316 variables (set of V_i ; diagnostic statistics obtained in the previous study), their diagnostic abilities (e.g.
317 relationships in Figs. 3 and 4) were re-examined. Accuracy statistics were not considered in this study
318 since they are not available from real experiments.

319

320 3.2.1. Anticipating the correct model (scenario)

321 The prior task is the anticipation of the correct model (identification of the true biodegradation
322 model; Table 1), since further predictions can only be approached if the correct scenario has been
323 assumed. A priori, this task could be performed experimentally. For instance, simple indicators of
324 microbial possible growth-linked biodegradation are the turbidity observed during the biodegradation
325 process, or better, the optical density (e.g. at 600 nm) measurement (Shuler and Kargi, 2002). On the
326 other hand, some possible experimental situations could make more difficult the decision making on
327 the right biodegradation model. For instance, the presence of “coincidental” carbon sources and
328 microbes resulting in microbial growth (Liu et al., 2014) and/or toxicity issues, both provoking pitfalls
329 in the kinetic model selection (see more details in Table S2 in supplementary data).

330 To help in the decision making process, the anticipative strategy was applied. An indicator
331 “IScenario” was set as the response variable and then, the suitable diagnostic statistics (predictor
332 variables) to calculate it were investigated. According to Fig. 2, for the two incorrect scenarios ([12]
333 and [21]), R^2 shows some discriminant ability between outputs obtained at low and high S_0 values
334 (i.e. such outputs are clustered in groups). Since this behaviour does not occur in the correct scenarios,
335 R^2 outputs obtained from two extreme substrate concentrations (i.e. two experiments in the practice)
336 could be connected with the incorrect (or correct) scenario. However, the use of R^2 alone to calculate
337 IScenario provided a limited discriminant ability. The combination of 100 R^2 (just to set it in the 0-
338 100 scale) with variables (Pp(S) and Dp) provided a more suitable discriminant function. Table 2

339 shows the results (IScenario threshold and f_i values). As can be seen, R^2 has the highest f_i value (twice
340 the other two weighting factors), indicating its maximum discriminant ability.

341 To evaluate the probabilities (success rates) associated with the IScenario > 0 threshold for a
342 “correct scenario” decision (Table 2), the 100 simulations at the highest S_0 level were combined with
343 the 100 simulations at the lowest S_0 level, totalling 10^4 results. The probabilities of “correct scenario”
344 decision were 98.5, 73.2, 1.4 and 1.7 % for scenarios [11], [22], [21] and [12], respectively. Thus, the
345 probabilities of anticipating the correct/incorrect scenario are reasonably high. Particularly, there is a
346 low probability (< 2 %) of accepting the incorrect model scenarios ([12] and [21]) as correct.

347

348 3.2.2. *Anticipating the correct (first- or mixed-order) region*

349 The anticipation of the region (first- or mixed-order) of a given experiment must be performed
350 once the correct scenario has been assumed (Table 2). Since Eq. (3b) in Table S1 should work fine
351 only for $S_0 \ll K_s$, it was evaluated as a predictive variable to anticipate the first- or mixed-region
352 situation. $R^2_{Eq.(3b)}$ presented insufficient discriminant ability (see Fig. S5 in supplementary data); so
353 the combination with other variables was evaluated. Concretely, for scenario [11], the combination
354 with $Pp(S)$ could be appropriate (see Fig. 2). A suitable combination of weighting factors of the two
355 predictive variables for calculating the proposed indicator “IRegion[11]”, and its threshold, is
356 depicted in Table 2. The decision of “mixed-order region” probabilities were 0, 0, 0, 99 and 100 %
357 for $\log(S_0/K_s) = -3, -2, -2, 0$ and 0.4 , respectively (100 simulations per level). Thus, the probability
358 of anticipating the correct region is high. For scenario [22] a suitable predictive variable (to combine
359 with $R^2_{Eq.(3b)}$) could be Dp (Fig. 1). Table 2 shows results for the new indicator “IRegion[22]”. From
360 them, the corresponding probabilities were 0, 0, 0, 89 and 100 % for $\log(S_0/K_s) = -3, -2, -2, 0$ and
361 0.4 , respectively. Again, the probability of anticipating the correct region is reasonably high. As stated
362 in Table 1, if the first-order region is anticipated, S_0 should be increased to obtain better scores of
363 accuracy and uncertainty.

364

365 3.2.3. *Anticipating the RSD level*

366 Up to now, RSD was prefixed at 5 %. However, in practice, the overall method imprecision
367 (including sources of uncertainty from the biodegradation and analytical processes) of a real
368 experiment is not investigated in many works. In order to study the RSD-statistics relationships,
369 additional simulations were performed fixing S_0/K_s at 2.5 (mixed region), a favourable situation if
370 the correct model has been selected (see Table 1). RSD was varied from 0.01 (too optimistic) to 10
371 % (more realistic).

372 Among the different statistics, MAE (or Pp(S)) and Up2 showed the best correlations with
373 RSD for the scenario [11] and [22], respectively (see Fig. S4 in supplementary data). In both cases,
374 the combination of these selected predictive variables with other variables did not improve the results,
375 so they were used alone to perform a direct RSD anticipation. Table 2 shows the proposed criteria.
376 However, it should be indicated that the dispersion of the estimated RSD values, related with the own
377 RSD level, was noticeable (see Fig. S6 in supplementary data). Thus, under- or over-estimations can
378 be obtained, particularly for $RSD > 5\%$ (imprecise real experiments). As indicated in Table 2, if the
379 estimated Up2 is higher than 100, an $RSD > 10$ is automatically assumed.

380

381 *3.3. Frequency and magnitude of errors for estimates in favourable conditions.*

382 Errors in the parameter estimates (Ep1 and Ep2) have positive and negative values (Pp does
383 not account for this sign). A study comprising 1000 simulations in favourable conditions (as in Fig.
384 S1, but only at $\log S_0 / K_s = 0.4$) and focused on scenarios [11] and [22] (correct model selection
385 cases), was performed to outline error probabilities. For both scenarios, Ep1 and Ep2 showed the
386 typical Gaussian frequency distribution, relatively centred on zero (see Fig. S7 in supplementary
387 data). Errors for the scenario [22] were mostly distributed in the ± 25 and $\pm 50\%$ for p1 and p2
388 estimates, respectively. However, some errors for the scenario [11] exceeded these limits, showing
389 an important concentration (34%) in the negative zone (unexpected according to the Gaussian trend).
390 This atypical group corresponds with the cluster observed in Fig. 1 for this scenario ($Pp \sim 40$ in the
391 Pp-Dp plot; section 3.1.3). In the case of p2, such errors approach the -100% level.

392 On the other hand, a relationship between Ep2 for scenario [11] and the statistics Dp and Pp(S)
393 was observed. Note that Ep1 and Ep2 correlated (as p1 and p2; see Figures S2-S4 in supplementary
394 data), being $Ep2 > Ep1$ in absolute values. Therefore, only the anticipation of Ep2 was intended. The
395 combination $Dp \times Pp(S) / 100$ was found to anticipate the Ep2 range (See Table 2). As can be seen
396 in Fig. 3, to ensure that Ep2 values are in the $\pm 50\%$ range, $Dp \times Pp(S) / 100$ values have to be above
397 80. For $Dp \times Pp(S) / 100 < 50$, Ep2 becomes unacceptable in many cases.

398 Fig. 3 also reveals a group of results with an almost constant Ep2 close to -100% (the most
399 frequent value is -95.5%). This group becomes a dangerous pitfall associated with the scenario [11].
400 For instance, for $Ep2 = +100\%$ (also found in Fig. 3), the estimated p2 is 10 (twice $K_s = 5$), but for
401 $Ep2 = -95.5\%$, p2 is 0.23, which differs from K_s in more than one order of magnitude. Such high
402 variability in Ep2 (thus in p2) is due to the prefixed RSD (an evidence of unreliability affecting to
403 accuracy). So, the criterion $Dp \times Pp(S) / 100 > 80$ in Table 2 becomes essential to limit the results for

404 p2 into the more acceptable 2.5 – 7.5 range ($Ep2 \pm 50\%$). This criterion is not necessary for scenario
405 [22], thus it is less risky.

406

407 3.4. *Effects on accuracy and reliability of other intrinsic parameters of Eq. (1a)*

408 In the case of using Eq. (1a), X_0 and Y must be also estimated. To the best of our knowledge,
409 the impact of these estimations on accuracy and reliability has not been established. X_0 and Y
410 estimations can be performed experimentally (e.g. Helbling et al., 2014), and thus, they can have
411 errors. The impact of simulated errors in X_0 and Y on the accuracy and reliability in the scenario [11]
412 was evaluated introducing systematic errors (of -10% and +10%). To see the net impact, RSD was
413 set to zero. The errors in the estimated parameters ($Ep1$ and $Ep2$) were of the same sign and magnitude
414 than the provoked X_0 -error. $Ep1$ and $Ep2$ outputs were of the same magnitude and opposite sign than
415 the provoked Y-error. In the case of provoked X_0 - and Y-errors of the same magnitude but of opposite
416 sign, $Ep1$ and $Ep2$ doubled the magnitude of the provoked errors, while perfectly correlated X_0 - and
417 Y-errors (same magnitude and sign) provided no impact on $Ep1$ and $Ep2$. At the $\pm 10\%$ error level
418 for X_0 and Y, maximum errors (for $Ep2$) were around 25%, with a low impact of other statistics (Dp ,
419 R^2 , $Pp(S)$). Table S5 in supplementary data shows these results. Therefore, X_0 - and Y-errors represent
420 a moderate pitfall (affecting mainly to the accuracy of estimates), except in the cases of high non-
421 correlated errors (e.g. for X_0 - and Y-errors of 20 and -20 %, respectively, $Ep2$ becomes 58.5 %).

422 As an alternative strategy, Y can be estimated computationally as a third parameter in Eq. (1a)
423 (Helbling et al., 2014; Liu and Zachara, 2001; Robinson and Tiedje, 1983). To the best of our
424 knowledge, the influence of estimating Y simultaneously with the Monod parameters has not been
425 evaluated. The impact of this additional estimation on $Pp-Dp$ and $Pp(S)-R^2$ plots was evaluated. The
426 simulations indicated that, in most cases, the estimation of Y worsened the $p1$ and $p2$ estimates in
427 terms of accuracy and uncertainty (an additional pitfall). However, in some few cases, the effect was
428 the opposite; confirming the unreliability associated to this strategy. Three typical results of this study
429 are shown in Fig. S8 supplementary data.

430

431 3.5. *Additional remarks*

432 It should be noted that this work focusses on the accuracy and reliability of $p1$ and $p2$
433 estimations. However, if the primary objective was just to have a curve with a good fit to the
434 experimental data (e.g. high R^2), both Monod and simplified Monod models would work well in many
435 cases (Table 1). Concretely, Fig. 2 shows that the worst R^2 values are above 0.75, in the current
436 conditions, even selecting the wrong model. This fact confers applicability to model the experimental

437 data, in spite of all the mentioned pitfalls. Concretely, a reasonable good S-t model could serve to
438 derive other related fitted curves, as biodegradation curves (BD-t), from which the half-life time, $t_{1/2}$,
439 can be estimated, alternatively to Eq. (3b) (see Table 1). In the case of the biodegradation of a chiral
440 compound, enantiomeric fraction, EF, curves (EF-t) could also be obtained (Escuder-Gilabert et al.,
441 2018).

442

443 **Conclusions**

444 Pitfalls in biodegradation model estimations become pitfalls in environmental and health risk
445 assessment. Simulation of concentration-time depletion data associated to biodegradation processes
446 is a requisite for accuracy estimation of Monod and related kinetic models and reveals their pitfalls
447 (e.g. anomalous outputs; non-comparable estimates between models, poor accuracy-uncertainty
448 correlation for estimates, etc.). These pitfalls become unacceptable when a favourable situation (i.e.
449 correct kinetic model, mixed-order region and imprecision level not higher than 5 %) is not satisfied.
450 In the presence of noisy data, a good R^2 or a low uncertainty of the estimates are not guaranty of
451 accuracy. These aspects could (and should) be anticipated before accepting estimations from real
452 biodegradation data, e.g. according to Table 2 rules. Even with a favourable situation, errors can fall
453 into the ± 50 level (for K_s estimates) or be higher using the Monod model at a data imprecision level
454 of 5 %.

455 The strategies proposed in this work are suggested as a guide to simulate data with other
456 kinetic parameters (μ_m or V_m and K_s values), number of data available, other imprecision conditions,
457 etc., compatible with a given experiment. From the simulation results obtained with the current
458 conditions, some general suggestions for environmental and health risk modellers can be established
459 concerning kinetic parameters estimation (after verifying/anticipating the use of the correct model):
460 (i) if the experiment falls into the first-order region, $\log(S_0 / K_s < 0)$, discard the estimation of the
461 parameters μ_m or V_m and K_s . If possible, increase S_0 to obtain more reliable estimates. Alternatively,
462 estimate the first-order constant (k), suitable in this situation, and use it for further health risk
463 assessment; (ii) if the measured (or anticipated) RSD level is higher than 5 %, try to improve it (use
464 other procedure with a higher precision or increase the number of replicates). In addition, if Monod
465 kinetics is assumed (scenario [11]): (iii) accept only results with $Dp \times Pp(S) / 100$ above 80; (iv) be
466 cautious with the experimental estimation of X_0 and Y , since they introduce moderate errors on the
467 estimates (except if they are directly correlated); (v) avoid the mathematical estimation of Y by the
468 Monod model since it worsens the quality of the μ_m - and K_s -estimates.

469 On the other hand, if the primary objective is just to fit a model to the experimental S-t data,
470 to derive half-life times for chemicals persistence estimations, both Monod and Michaelis-Menten-
471 like equations could be used, using the one providing the best R^2 . If X_0 and Y are unknown, Eq. (2b)
472 could be used. Since it is explicit in S , it has an additional advantage for experimental S-t profiles not
473 reaching zero, for which an offset term can be used (Table 1). A priori, environmental and health risk
474 estimates (e.g. pollutant persistence) should be more accurate if derived from half-life time estimates
475 than from kinetic parameter estimations.

476

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481

482 **References**

483

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548

549 **Figure captions**

550

551 **Fig. 1.** Predictive vs. descriptive power (Pp-Dp) plots for each scenario and $\log(S_0 / K_s)$ levels
552 studied: -3 (∇), -2 (\triangleleft), -1 (\square), 0 (\bullet) and 0.4 (+). S_0 , initial pollutant concentration; K_s , half-saturation
553 or Monod constant.

554

555 **Fig. 2.** Predictive power for the concentration data vs. determination coefficient (Pp(S)- R^2) plots for
556 each scenario. Symbols as in Fig. 1.

557

558 **Fig. 3.** $D_p \times P_s(S) / 100$ as indicator to anticipate error levels in p2 estimate (Ep2) in scenario [11]
559 from a 1000-simulations study in favourable conditions (as described in section 2.1 for the $S_0 / K_s =$
560 0.4 level). Vertical lines correspond to $D_p \times P_p(S) / 100$ levels of 80 and 50. Some higher error values
561 are not plotted. D_p , descriptive power; $P_s(S)$, predictive power for the concentration data.

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578 Fig. 3.

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Table 2

595

Results corresponding to the anticipative strategies

Assumed Scenario	Predictive Variables	Anticipation	Response variable and threshold Decision
-	$R^2, Pp(S), Dp$ (at two extreme S_0 values)	Scenario	$I_{Scenario} > 0$ ^a Correct scenario
[11]	$R^2_{Eq. (3b)}, Pp(S)$	Region	$I_{Region[11]} > 92$ ^b Mixed-order (otherwise first-order)
[22]	$R^2_{Eq. (3b)}, Dp$	Region	$I_{Region[22]} > 0$ ^c Mixed-order (otherwise first-order)
[11]	MAE	RSD	$RSD \sim 0.7 MAE$
[22]	Up2	RSD	For $Up2 > 100$, $RSD > 10$; otherwise $RSD \sim 0.13 Up2$
[11]	$Dp, Pp(S)$	$Ep2$ ^d	$Dp \times Pp(S) / 100 > 80$ $Ep2$ inside $\pm 50\%$

596

^a $I_{Scenario} = (f_1 100 R^2 + f_2 Pp(S) + f_3 Dp)_{High-S_0} - (f_1 100 R^2 + f_2 Pp(S) + f_3 Dp)_{Low-S_0}$. A suitable weighting

597

factor combination is $f_1 = 0.55, f_2 = 0.25$ and $f_3 = 0.2$.

598

^b $I_{Region[11]} = f_1 100 R^2_{Eq. (3b)} + f_2 Pp(S)$. A suitable weighting factor combination is $f_1 = -0.5, f_2 = 1.5$

599

^c $I_{Region[22]} = f_1 100 R^2_{Eq. (3b)} + f_2 Dp$. A suitable weighting factor combination is $f_1 = -0.5, f_2 = 1.5$

600

^d $Ep1$ is always better than $Ep2$, and they are correlated.

601